

DERIVATIVE ANALYSIS OF VOCABULARY IN THE EXPLANATORY DICTIONARY “CHAROGI HIDOYAT”

Juraev Ilyos Ruzikulovich

PhD researcher, Samarkand State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10519846>

Abstract. *The concept of derivation is equated with the term word formation in expressing word formation processes. Word formation is an object of language that has been studied since historical times. The enrichment of the lexical structure of the language is directly related to the process of word formation, and this phenomenon opens up wide opportunities not only for the development of the language, but also for the development of society. Studying the processes of historical derivation of languages on the example of classic dictionaries is especially important in illuminating historical derivation. The derivational study of the text of classic dictionaries in the lexicographical aspect is extremely important in the study of the processes of language development. This article is dedicated to the study of the derivation of the explanatory dictionary “Charogi hidoyat”.*

Keywords: *concept of derivation, word formation, Derivatology, dictionary Charogi hidoyat, paremiological units.*

It is known that word formation is one of the separate independent fields of linguistics, which includes new word formation, word formation in the historical development of the language, phenomena related to word formation and word formation methods. Today, the field of “Derivatology”, which has become a unique independent field of linguistics, is also used in the lexical plan, that is, in the context of word formation [1; 5]. The process of studying historical derivation is important in educating the young generation with a broad and comprehensive worldview, as well as in knowing and applying the socio-linguistic history of nations as a person of high intelligence.

The dictionary “Charogi hidoyat” (in the following places it is abbreviated as ChH, and the page of the source is given in square brackets) is a lexicographic work created in Hindustan by Sirojiddin Alikhan Orzu (1687 - 1757) in 1734, in which 2279 lexical, syntactic and paremiological units are explained. Morphologically, the vocabulary of all word groups is included in the dictionary, and the main part of the dictionary is noun and adjective word groups. It is known that there are four types of word formation in Tajik literary language: morphological, morphological-syntactic, lexical-syntactic, lexical-semantic. Morphological, morphological-syntactic word formation from these is very fruitful [4; 15].

Lexical units explained in the dictionary (45.3% of 1027) from the structural-grammatical point of view consist of basic, artificial, compound (complex subordinate, complicating compound) words, the statistics of which are as follows:

Basic words 403 (39, 3%);

Artificial words 268 (26%);

Compound words 356 (34, 7%).

Basic words: *abir, amn, ang, axm, baland, bam, bast, bob, bod, bol, bor, voya, go‘y, dam, dan, dang, dasht, did, duk, yod, yol, zar, zot, zog‘* and etc.

Дам — (ба фатх) нафас ва ба маънии вақт низ. Ва аксар истеъмоли он дар таркиб бо лафзи субҳ дида шуда ва гоҳе бо шом низ, i.e. Dam – (with conquest) in the sense of breath and time. Its use is often observed in the composition of the words "subh" and "evening". The author derives this word from the word "damidan" as well as in ancient times *shom* emphasizes the contradictory use of the word "subhdam" in the sense of time [5; 105]; Бол – бозуи қонварон; ва гоҳе ба маънии пар, ки ба арабӣ риш гӯянд низ *маҷозан* омада (Bol – wing of animals; sometimes they say "rish" in Arabic in the figurative sense of par... (Rubai from Salim) [31]); Дӯш – шаби гузаштаи мутгасили имрӯз; ва онро шаби дӯш ва шаби дӯшина низ гӯянд (Dosh [دوش] – They say that today and night are continuous (tunov), shabi dosh, shabi doshina [107]. The author provides “duk” an encyclopedic explanation of this word. It gives detailed information about the making, shape, function, method of use of this instrument, its Hindi translation "takla" and quotes a verse from Saifi in the description of the silk spinner.

Basic words are mainly nouns and adjectives, as well as verbs, verbs (*dosh*), pronouns (*manro*, *turo*, *inho*, *hud*, *hash*, *chandho*, *chunon*), auxiliary (*az*, *to*, *ham*), conjunction (*but*, *perhaps*), number (*chil* - 40), introductory word (*ore*, *na*) etc. Artificial words 268 (59 are currently in use) [2; 54] is made by different methods of derivation. Including words made with the help of suffixes: *-iy/-giy* (گی) (*-lik*) suffix is very productive in word formation, 150 words were formed with this suffix. This additional noun forms nouns of belonging and task from a group of words, nouns representing activities and various relationships from passive and compound adjectives, relative adjectives and past tense verbs [4; 153]. 5 words with suffix *-gi* (*aftodagi*, *raftagi*, *tanghavsalagi*, *narmodagi*, *borangi*) is made using the suffix “*hoi mukhtafi*” - added after the vowel *a*. This supplement is one of the most active supplements. In some sources, words such as *yor+furo'sh+iy*, *boryo+posh+iy*, *hoya+gaz+ak*, *hino+band+on*, *yor+furosh+on* are also compound words. interpreted as [2; 62], however, in the grammatical works of the Tajik language, this type of word formation was not seen, so we noted these words as made-up words. From the words formed by the compositional method, noun+present tense verb [2; 62], also, *ism+h. z.f. +-iy* (عی), *-ak*, *-a*, *-on* words formed in the form can be formed. The suffix *-iy* (*-ī*) is especially important in the way this word is formed, and 33 words were formed with this suffix: *boryoposhi*, *yarfuroshi* [2; 62]. In addition, there are types of word formation using this method, such as noun+noun, adjective+noun, noun+pronoun. One of the productive suffixes in the Tajik language is *-a*, which serves to form nouns, adjectives, adverbs and adjectives (*nima*, *nishina*, *zanjira*, *vomonda*, *kanora*, *duda*, *kushta*, *dorudasta*, *barfuftoda*), with the help of this suffix 39 the word is made up. *-ana* (as *khasmona*, *pahrezona*, *salomona*) 5, *-ina* 1 (*sabzina*), *-gor* 1 (*rozgor*), *-ak* 8 (*dastak*, *lachak*, *kayak*, *simak*), *-bon* (*pushtibon*), *-bor* 4, *-dar* 4, *-don* 5 (*surmadon*), *-soz* 1, *-goh* 5 (*table*, *gardangoh*, *pursegoh*), *-gar* 4 (*paper*), *-chi* 1 (*kadaganchi*), *-istan* 1 (*Ahriston*), *-vora* 1 (*goshvora*), *-ish* 4, *-on* 5 (*afshon*, *bozon*, *lakshon*, *junbon*) are made using suffixes, many of them have undergone a semantic change. For example, *Dastgoh* – in the sense of investment and mockery is given, this word in modern Tajik and Uzbek languages means “tool, machine, equipment”, but is not used in the sense of “investment and mockery” [3; 155].

There are very few words in the dictionary made by means of prefixes, and they are as follows: *bar-*3 (*barhazar*, *barkhostan*, *bardoshtan*), *be-* (*bedavlat*, *bezor*, *betah*, *besarafsar*, *besutun*) in the composition of words 5 *ta*, *vo-* 10 (from *vokashi*, *vosokhtan*, *vomondan*, *vobosidan*...), *no-* 4 (*noras*, *nokhan*, *nodurust*, *noguzir*), *ham-* 3 (*hamdomon*, *hamgir*, *hamchu*), *dar-* 3 prefixes *ta* (from *dargardi*, *dargiriftan*, *income*) were also involved, and the words formed

with the help of these suffixes performed almost the same function as the meaning of the words in the modern Tajik language.

Compound words: In the dictionary, there are more words made in the compositional way than artificial words, they are 356, and if we classify them according to the grammatical terms of the Tajik language, there are connected complex words (*kalimai* compound *payvast* - double and repeated words) and subordinate complex words (*kalimahoi* complexi subordinate - complex) are divided into such types.

There are 29 compound words that are linked: *kardivu murdiy*, *damu po'st*, *yolu kupol*, *chanoruma'nor*, *rogurang*, *saropo*, *sarosar*, *shaddumad*, *taq-taq*, *arrugur*, *qar-qar*, *nat'utasht*, *na'ludog'*, *hachchumach*, *zudbud* and etc. The main feature for this type of words is that the relationship between the components is equal, which is not the case in compound words. The formation of connected compound words is also based on several patterns, and we can see this in the example of words in the dictionary. The connecting link is formed using the suffix u sound: *damu po'st*, *yolu kupol*, *chanoruma'nor*, *rogurang*, *shaddumad*, *arrugur*, *nat'utasht*, *na'ludog*, *hachchumach*, *uftuxez*, *fannufaraj*, *chapurost*, *vaqtu soat*, *lakulunj*, *surxusiyoh*. Вақту соат – чизест ки авқоту соёоти лайлу наҳор аз он маълум шавад; ва дар Ҳиндустон онро гҳарияли фарангӣ гӯянд... (Vaqtu soat (time) – something, night and day times are determined from it; and in India it is called "ghariyali farangi"... [215]).

By means of the vowel o, which is used as a connecting link: *saropo*, *sarosar*, *kashmakashon*, *chapurost*. Саросар – тамошо ва сайри чое аз сар то по (Sarosar – walking around a place from head to toe (quoted from Yahya Koshi) [128]).

The appearance of words through repetition, it is similar to repeated words in Uzbek: *Bog'-bog'*, *push-push*, *kalmakal*, *roh roh*, *taqtaq*, *tak-tak*, *ug'-ug'*, *finfin*, *qarqar*. The formation of such words is not as prolific as it is in modern Tajik language, and we can observe that it occurs mainly in colloquial speech.

Taqtaq – bread type. Byte in paper from Vahid:

Чу тақтак бувад коғази нони ӯ,

Бар ин нон чаҳонест меҳмони ӯ.

It is clear from the meaning of the above poem that taqtak is a type of thin bread; and it is understood that it is also used in the sense of sound [151]. We can learn from the given example that this word is qatqat, it is made of folded thin, we think that the misunderstanding of the structural meaning of the words and the imitation of the sounds in the breaking of bread caused the sound change.

Compound words explained in the dictionary are 118 out of 327 words [2; 61] word is actively used in modern Tajik language. It is very convenient to form words in this way, and it involves nouns, adjectives, verbs, adjectives and pronouns.

These compound words also differ structurally:

Forming using a noun + present tense verb base (command verb). In the formation of this word, the second part of the word expresses the main meaning and explains some aspect of the word in the first part, mainly it expresses the characteristics and functions of a person or thing: *oinador*, *chashmband*, *xoksho*, *xishtmol*, *damkash*, *rasanboz*, *ravzaxon*, *serobapaz*, *suratboz*, *surohiboz*, *tosboz*, *atrfurosh* and etc.

A compound word formed in the form of noun-noun.

The words formed in this way mainly denote the name of the subject: obdandon, otashbarg, pardagilem, peshdoman, dostro, sarsuxan, Farahobod. Basically, 11 place names were formed using the word "khana", which represents the name of a place.

Form using adjective+noun. Many words in the dictionary are formed in this way. The words made in this way express a feature, a sign, a form: *badxob*, *tozasikka*, *tangaysh*, *tangro*, *kalonkor*, *garmsut*, *girdbolish*, *girdaksaroy*, *sabukpo*, *narmshona*, *navqadam*. Гирдаксарой – чое ки барои наварӯс ва домод созанд; ва ба арабӣ ҳаҷла гӯянд (*Girdaksaroy* – The place prepared for the new bride and groom (*goshana*), in Arabic it is called *hajla*. [180]); Навқадам – тифли нав ба рафтор омада (*Navqadam* – walking an infant [209]).

Forming using noun+adjective. D.Badridinov said that this type of word formation is not very typical of the Tajik literary language, that is, in these words, the constituent parts have changed places [2; 67]: *xonasiyoh*, *rishsafed*, *rosafed* kabi.

Ришсафед – маъруф; ва низ раис ва муаммар, ки арбоб низ гӯянд (*Rishsafed* – elder person; They also say *rais*, *muammarmarkim*, *arbob* (*Bayt* from *Ashraf*) [117]).

Forming with a noun and an adjective. Basically, exaggerated words are isolated: *zarbasta*, *ramzada*, *ro'boxta*, *sarzinda*, *sarburrida*, *sarrafta*, *chashmxo'rd*. Сармосӯхта – чизе ки аз шиддати сармо зоеъ ва табох шавад, хоҳ наботот, хоҳ ҳайвонот (*Sarmosoxta* – the one who died in the frost - an animal that was hit by the cold (*Bayt* from *Tughra*) [129]).

With noun+number. In such compound words, the noun expresses the main meaning, and the number explains some aspect of it: *Hazorjarib*, *hazorpesha*, *hazordona*, *chor mazhab*, *chorxam*, *chorshona*, *chorgul*, *chorjoma*; *chilcharog*, *chilsutun*, *sipora*, *saddahon*, *sadbarg*, *dahmardakor*, *haftjosh*, *dutegaboz*. (*Chorgul* - footprint of a sarcastic dog; from conversation, they will burn me [76]).

There is also a three-word compound word in the dictionary: *kalla+pur+bod+iy*, *dah+mard+a+kor* kabi.

In the dictionary, researched from the colloquial language, it is explained as "Dahmardakor - a person who takes care of the work of many people", this word is still used in the dialect and means a *skilled shepherd* [108].

In short, the lexical units explained in the dictionary are 1027 (45, 3%), structural-grammatical basic words (403 - 39, 3%), artificial words (356 - 34, 7%) and compound words (268 - 26%).

Basic words, mainly nouns and adjectives, as well as verbs, adverbs, and pronouns (*manro*, *turo*, *inho*, *xud*, *xesh*, *chandho*, *chunon*), conjunction (*az*, *to*, *ham*), connectors (*lekin*, *balki*), number (*chil* – 40, *miatayn* – 200), introductory words (*ore*, *na*) and etc.

Artificial words: made using suffixes like *-iy/-giy* (گی) (-lik) 150 *-a* 39, *-ona* 5, *-ina* 1 (*sabzina*), *-gor* 1 (*rozgor*), *-ak* 8, *-bon* (*pushtibon*), *-bor* 4, *-dor* 4, *-don* 5, *-soz* 1, *-goh* 5, *-gar* 4, *-chi* 1 (*qadaganchi*), *-iston* 1 (*Ahriston*), *-vora* 1 (*goshvora*), *-ish* 4, *-on* 5.

There are very few words in the dictionary made by means of prefixes: *bar* -3, *be* - 5, *vo* -10, *no*- 4, *ham*- 3, *dar*- 3 prefixes were involved, and the words formed with the help of these additions performed almost the same function as the meaning of the words in the current Tajik language.

In the dictionary, there are 356 words made by compositional method, 29 of them are connected complex words.

REFERENCES

1. Turniyozov N.Q “O‘zbek tili derivatsion sintaksisiga kirish. Samarqand. – 1990.
2. Бахриддинов Д. “Чароғи Ҳидоят”-и Орзу ва забони тоҷикии форсӣ (монография) – Душанбе, 1992. – 104 с.
3. Грамматикаи забони адабии ҳозираи тоҷик. Ҷ. I. – Душанбе: “Дониш”, 1985. – 356 с.
4. Забони адабии ҳозираи тоҷик. Қисми 1. Лексикология. Фонетика. Морфология. – Душанбе: Ирфон, 1982. – 462 с.
5. Орзу, Сирочуддин Алихон. Чароғи хидоят. Таҳияи матн бо пешгуфтор, тавзеҳот ва луғатномаи Амон Нуров. – Душанбе: Ирфон, 1992. – 288 с.
6. آرزو، سراخ الدين على خان. چراغ هدايهت. – نولکشور، 1930. – 112 ص.